

Impact of Terrorism on FDI Inflow in Pakistan- A Time Series Analysis

Author Details: Sadaf Mustafa

Assistant Professor-Department Of Commerce-University of Karachi

Abstract:

Finance is needed to grow every sector of life. The internal finance can be raised through public saving, direct and indirect taxes, etc. while the external sources of finance include foreign direct investment and loans from the foreign and local lending institutions. Foreign direct investment is considered very important as an external source of finance as it has long term effects in both quantitative and qualitative terms and doesn't need to be paid off back with heavy interest charges like in the case of loans. FDI plays a key role in bringing capital, advanced technology, skills transfer and increase standard of living in developing countries. Pakistan as a developing country needs a huge amount of finance for development and non-development expenditures. With its heavy budgetary deficits, the country took and is still taking loans from different lending institutions. The country didn't focus on raising FDI in the starting decades, but then it realized the importance. Over the last two decades, Pakistan has also made significant efforts in increasing the flow of foreign investment. However, the country has suffered terrible terrorism after the 9/11 attacks which have also impacted the flow of investment in the country. Terrorism is the actions of the people who are working against the law and the government. The flow of investment a decade before and after the 9/11 terror attacks has been analyzed that had hit the country with massive terrorism disrupting the economic scenario

Key Words: Pakistan, FDI, Terrorism

Literature Review:

Foreign direct investment inserts many positive effects on the development of the economy of any country. Hence, Pakistan is also working to raise the inflow of foreign investment in the country. But country suffered from huge terrorism right after partnering the USA in its war against terrorism that has affected the inflow of FDI and economy. The literature intends to analyze the effects of terrorism on the inflow of foreign direct investment in Pakistan.

Introduction:

Pakistan is a gifted land with huge natural resources. But the country is still striving to get its economy on the track. The economic condition of Pakistan is always in a fluctuating position due to bad economic policies and other factors like natural disasters, terrorism and unstable law and order situation. In the early years of Pakistan, the economic policies had not been made focusing on many core essentials on which FDI is on the top. Pakistan has always focused on loans and aids. The foreign direct investment inflow in Pakistan has not been very satisfactory in Pakistan till the 1980s. The country has not realized the importance of FDI for the economic development till then, but at the end of the 20th century, the country has made significant efforts to partner with the foreign countries to develop its economy and here the liberal investment regime has begun (Farooq and Shahzad, 2015)¹. Foreign direct investment plays a key role in economic development which includes not just numbers but also by providing social benefit through enhancing the standard of living of people. FDI ensures capital transfer, transfer of technology, skills transfer, contribute to tax generation as well as provide people with employment opportunities (Lemi, 2004)²

Pakistan has been trying greatly to get the FDI to earn benefits from it but the wave of terrorism that hit Pakistan in the first decade of the 21st century after 9/11 has diminished the inflow of FDI in Pakistan even after the liberal investment regime of the country. Terrorism has caused huge loss of precious lives and money. Pakistan engagement in the War against terrorism made the country to pay much cost³. The Afghan and Pakistani Taliban both have done several suicides and timed bomb blast. At 16 December 2014, the attack

terrorists at school in Peshawar killing more than 150 students and teachers will be remarked as the saddest incident of Pakistani history. But after the incident now, Pakistan is trying to remove all the terrorists more aggressively from Pakistan under its operation “Zarb e Azb” which was initiated when terrorist attacked Jinnah International Airport of Karachi. Pakistan is working harder to remove the terrorists from its land, and the forces have succeeded to some extent in achieving this target (Javaid, 2015)⁴. The result can be seen in the form of China Pakistan Economic Corridor that is expected to change the economic condition of Pakistan widely.

Advantages of Foreign Direct Investment

A huge amount of finance is required to fulfill the capital needs in all the countries. The foreign direct investment plays a vital role in bridging the capital gap especially in the developing countries where the high expenditures for development make the budgetary deficit often very high. The saving in the developing economies is also low due to low per capita income hence resulting in the poor domestic investment and here is the vacant place where the investments from foreign firms play their part. The other advantages from FDI include providing employment opportunities to the skilled and unskilled labor of the countries as well as enhancement of the managerial and technical skills of labor and managers. It also hence results in the improvement in the rate of public and private savings. The developing countries also lack advance technology which lag them behind in the international trading markets and FDI become a source for technological transfer also (Contessi and Weinberger, 2009)⁵. This also leads to improvement in the productivity at the production made at the domestic level. The foreign firms also provide the people with quality products according to the international standards. The very important benefit of FDI is that it improves the balance of payment of the developing countries by lowering its imports and increasing the exports. The mandatory requirement for the foreign firms in terms of Corporate Social Responsibility also provides the poor people with health, educational and vocational facilities that improve their lives (Kastrati, 2013)⁶.

Pakistan in its early years doesn't give much attention to the foreign investment; hence the doors for foreign investors remained close. But in the 1990s Pakistan has liberalized its economic policies by providing chances to foreign investors to invest in the country (Khan and Kim, 1999)⁷. The country has put its much effort in increasing flow of investment by eliminating the equity caps and by providing the tax rebates. The following table shows the flow of investment in Pakistan from 1994 to 1999.

Net Inflow of FDI (Million US\$)

Year	FDI	FDI as %age of GDP	From USA	From UK	From Japan
1994-95	442.4	1.74	176.4	38.7	16.3
1995-96	1101.7	1.10	319.8	33.7	82.1
1996-97	682.1	0.79	-	-	-
1997-98	601.3	0.75	256.6	135.3	17.8
1998-99	472.3	0.77	214.62	89.3	59.0
1999-2000	469.9	0.55	166.9	169.0	17.7

(Source: Farooq and Khan, 2014⁸)

The above table shows that the flow of foreign direct investment in Pakistan in the year 1994 was \$442.4 million that was 1.74% of the GDP of the country in which the USA contributed the highest share that amounted to \$176.4 million. In the year 1995, the FDI rose to \$1101.7 million, but the GDP of the country was relatively high this year hence the FDI accounted for only 1.10% of the Gross Domestic Product and here also the share of USA was the highest which sent \$319.8 million in Pakistan in the form of FDI. In 1996 in Pakistan, the FDI fall to \$682.1 million that made up 0.79% of the GDP in which the USA, UK, and Japan had no contribution at all. In the next year of 1998, the FDI in Pakistan had fall to \$472.3 million which accounted for 0.77% of the GDP where the USA contributed for \$214.62 million. In the year 1999, the FDI further fall to

\$469.9 million which was only 0.55% of the GDP, the lowest on record in the period from 1994-1999. The USA contributed \$166.9 million in 1999. The table shows that the flow of FDI has increased after 1995 and started to fall in 1996 wherein 1999, the FDI was lowest since liberalization due to the successful attempt of atomic technology attainment by the country against the wills of the leaders of international markets.

The flow of foreign direct investment as discussed above has fallen after Pakistan became the first Muslim country to have the atomic power against the desires of the many countries of the globe. However, the world scenario completely changed in the very start of the 21st century when the United States of America suffered from the terrorist attacks commonly called as the 9/11 attacks. The USA soon launched a war against the terrorists and Pakistan became the ally of the “War of Terror.” Pakistan gave its whole support to the United States in its war against the terrorism but this support involved Pakistan in dreadful terrorism in itself. The country faced major terrorist attacks that caused the lives of thousands of people that include the civilians and the armed forces. The war also shut down the business activities in many tribal areas, and the whole country’s business activities were hurt badly. The USA launched many grants programs to pay Pakistan for its role in the USA’s war, but the disturbed trade activity and especially the loss of precious lives of the locals can never be counted in monetary terms.

The following table shows terrorist attacks in Pakistan from 2000-2011 and the FDI inflow in the country in context with the same years.

Table 5.1: Terrorism data and FDI of last 12 years				
Years	No of attacks	Casualties	Injuries	Net Inflow of FDI in Pakistan in \$
2000	15	79	316	308,000,000
2001	63	48	342	383,000,000
2002	35	68	299	823,000,000
2003	41	34	155	534,000,000
2004	137	255	1040	1,118,000,000
2005	245	210	571	2,201,000,000
2006	300	359	766	4,273,000,000
2007	678	1078	2484	5,590,000,000
2008	599	1251	3073	5,438,000,000
2009	500	1668	4312	2,338,000,000
2010	473	1547	3581	2,016,000,000
2011	639	1092	2633	3,015,000,000

(Source:

Shahbaz, Javed, Dar, Sattar, ⁹⁾

The above table can be analyzed year by year terrorist attacks and the death occurred in comparison with the inflow of FDI in Pakistan.

2000: In this year, the terrorist attacks in the country were counted at 15 which took lives of 79 people and 316 were injured. The FDI inflow in the country amounted to \$308 million that was very low due to sanctions imposed on Pakistan after the atomic technology was acquired.

2001: In the following year, the FDI inflow in the country was recorded at \$383 million that increased in comparison with 2000. The terrorist attacks in the year counted at 63 which caused the life of 48 people and left 342 people injured.

2002: In the year of 2002, after the horrific 9/11 attacks in the United State of America, the number of terrorist attacks in Pakistan have fallen that were recorded at 35 killing 68 people and injuring 299. The FDI inflow in this year has more than doubled from the previous year amounting to \$823 million.

2003: The FDI inflow in this year again fall to \$534 million and the number of terrorist attacks in the country increased to 41 that killed 34 and injured 155 civilians and army personnel.

2004: In this year, the war against terror partnering effects actually was seen. The number of terrorist attacks was recorded at 137 that caused the lives of 255 people and injured 1040 people. The amount of FDI that inflow in the following year was recorded at \$1,118 million.

2005: In the year of 2005, the FDI inflow again approximately doubled from 2004, amounting to \$2,201 million. The terrorist attacks recorded in the year were 245 that caused the life of 210 people leaving 571 people injured.

2006: In this year, the number of terrorist attacks rose to 300 which killed 359 people and injured 766. The FDI inflow further doubled to \$4,273 million.

2007: The year 2007 was one of the deadly years in the history in which Pakistan suffered from 678 attacks, the highest number of attacks in the period of 12 years. This caused the lives of 1078 innocent civilians and security forces. In this year, the FDI inflow was recorded at the highest figure that amounted to \$5,590 million.

2008: In the year 2008, 599 terrorist attacks were recorded that killed 1251 people and left 3073 people injured. The FDI inflow hence started to fall after the terrorist attacks increased in the country and amounted to \$5,438 million.

2009: In this year, the number of terrorist attacks was downed but the year was deadliest of the history of Pakistan. 500 terrorist attacks were recorded in this year but the number of casualties amounted to 1668, and 4312 people were injured in these attacks. The FDI inflow in the country went by half due to the high terrorism rate in the country that was recorded at \$2,338 million.

2010: In the following year, the number of terrorist attacks and casualties were declined a bit that was recorded as 473 terrorist attacks in the country killing 1547 people and leaving 3581 injured. The FDI inflow in this year further fell to \$2,016 million as due to the continuing terrorism, the foreign investors didn't find the country suitable for bringing in their investments.

2011: In the year 2011, the terrorist attacks rose to 639 in number that killed 1092 innocent people and left 2633 people injured. The FDI inflow increased in the following year amounting to \$3,015 million due to continuous efforts the country was making to increase the investment level that has fallen due to the deadly terrorism.

Image Enhancement Policy 2013-2017

Pakistan has liberalized its investment policy in the 1990s to increase the inflow of foreign investment being lacking capital which is an important need for development purpose (Khan and Nawaz, 2010¹⁰). Many investment policies have then been used according to the ideologies of changing governments. In 2013, the new government took over the country which has launched an investment policy for its 5 years tenure. The policy focused on increasing the inflow of investment in Pakistan. The basic essentials in the current policy which is implemented now are reducing the cost of starting and operating the business in Pakistan as well as creating links between all the factors involved in doing businesses like fiscal and monetary policy, industrial and trade policies, etc. (Board of Investment, 2013¹¹).

Pakistan has suffered from the great loss of lives and money from the war of terrorism where it is an ally of the United States. The partnering with the United States has initially increased the inflow of foreign direct investment in Pakistan from the US as well as the other allies like the United Kingdom, France, Germany, Japan, etc. When the outcomes of war started to come in the country, the foreign investment inflow started to reduce in Pakistan. There were many terrorist attacks in the country that destroyed the business environment

and investors were reluctant to bring in their investment that reduced the inflow of foreign investment in the country. The current investment policy focusses on image enhancement of the country where it arranges the visit of investors in Pakistan that are interested and looking for investment places around the globe (Board of Investment, 2013¹²). The purpose is to better the image of Pakistan in the minds of investors so that they find Pakistan as the most suitable place for investment. The Board of Investment also conducts trade fairs around the globe for this purpose. It has also launched one window facility where investors can have any information that is required for an investment decision. This all is to increase the inflow of FDI in Pakistan so that the country can get its benefits to get the economy on the right track.

Zarb-e-Azb

Pakistan has been in war from many years starting from cold and proxy war in the 1980s that made Afghans enter in Pakistan. This war condition from up to 3 decades has disturbed the economy of the country widely reducing the investment in the country (Hooper and Leguen, 2014¹³). Pakistan to fight from a strong wave of terrorism causing loss of lives and money started an operation called Zarb-e-Azb. Before starting the operation, Pakistan also brings the matter into parliament passing a Protection of Pakistan bill (Pakistan Governance Forum, 2014). The operation impacted passing in many ways. The operation resulted in migrants from the Taliban captured areas whose settlement cost a great sum of money. The spending on the military in the budget has also increased which resulted in a lesser budget in development purposes. The operation however impacted the country in good ways eradicating many militants from the Taliban captured areas and having control over them again, especially in North Waziristan. The impact of operation can be seen with an increase of investment as well as the CPEC which is expected to change the economic position of Pakistan greatly.

China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC)

The CPEC is a project of not just rails and roads, but it's a door to enter in the right track of economy (Ahmar, 2015). CPEC is considered as the largest investment of China in any foreign country which will change the whole region entirely by bringing economic prosperity not only in China and Pakistan but all the trading partners of China as well. Pakistan will get benefits in terms of infrastructure, employment, power projects, etc.

Current Position

The following table shows the position of foreign direct investment inflow for the period of 5 years from 2012 to 2016. The table is used to analyze the effects of terrorism in Pakistan in terms of FDI inflow and how the ongoing operation against terrorist in Pakistan, Zarb-e-Azb, has impacted the inflow of investment. The China Pakistan Economic Corridor decision will also be under consideration in analyzing the table.

Country	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16 (Jul-Apr)
USA	227.7	227.1	212.1	209.0	(75.7)
UK	205.8	633.0	157.0	174.3	57.9
U.A.E	36.6	22.5	(47.1)	216.4	137.2
Japan	29.7	30.1	30.1	71.1	18.2
Hong Kong	80.3	242.6	228.5	83.4	129.4
Switzerland	127.1	149.0	209.8	2.8	72.8
Saudi Arabia	(79.9)	3.2	(40.1)	(64.8)	(81.0)
Germany	27.2	5.5	(5.7)	(20.3)	(32.4)
Korea (South)	25.4	25.8	24.4	14.3	(15.1)
Norway	(275.0)	(258.4)	(21.6)	2.7	33.7
China	126.1	90.6	695.8	255.3	549.9
Others	289.7	285.5	224.4	(93.0)	221.4
Total including Pvt. Proceeds	820.7	1,456.5	1,667.6	851.2	1,016.3
Privatisation Proceeds	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
FDI Excluding Pvt. Proceeds	820.7	1,456.5	1,698.6	851.2	1,016.3

(Source: Board of Investment, 2016¹⁶)

The above table shows that in the year 2012, the FDI inflow was only \$620 million where the major investment was from USA, UK, Switzerland and China. In 2013, the FDI inflow increased to \$1456 million that is more than double from the previous year. Here, the UK accounted for the most investment; USA, Hong Kong and Switzerland were on the 2nd, 3rd and 4th position respectively. China invested in Pakistan, but it was not very noticeable. In 2014, when the new government implemented the new investment policy, China sent the most foreign direct investment in Pakistan that amounted to \$695 million out of the total FDI in Pakistan of \$1696 million. However, in 2015, the investment inflow fell badly and Pakistan received only \$851.2 million FDI. Here again, China was the largest contributor to FDI. The decrease in investment was due to ongoing terrorism that has effected the business environment widely. In the same year, MoUs for CPEC was signed. In 2016, the investment was around \$1 billion which has increased as a result of operation Zarb-e-Azb showing that Pakistan is trying to get the rid of terrorists and making the business environment gradually better. The main investment was from China with which Pakistan has signed the CPEC agreement. The USA and Saudi Arabia have withdrawn its investment which has two factors behind. Saudi Arabia is suffering from an oil price crisis as well as bad relations with Iran. USA is angry over the CPEC agreement that resulted in investment withdrawal from Pakistan. The good impact of CPEC on the economy and basically the investment inflow is yet to come.

Conclusion

Pakistan has suffered a lot after getting hit by the terrorism. The terrorism not only caused the country to lost precious lives of the civilians and the army forces and left many of them handicapped but also handicapped its economy. The country's economy that was not doing very good even after implementing the liberalized economic policies, the economy got more sluggish after the terrorism. The FDI that has many advantages like capital inflow, availability of advanced technology, employment increment, skills transfers, etc. also went down. The business environment was thus in huge trouble, the industries were shut down, and the inflation rate went high that declined the purchasing power of the country leaving people poorer. The employment level in the country has also fallen that increased the crime rates affecting the law and order situation. The FDI inflow in the beginning after being the partner in the USA's war against terrorism had increased from the USA, UK and the other partners of the USA but as the terrorist attacks increased, the investors repatriated their investment from the country. The foreign investors invest in only those countries where they found their investment to be safe, relatively risk free and expected to give higher returns. The situation of Pakistan being in high trouble declined the foreign direct investment level. The FDI inflow had thus found to be decreased in the country when the terrorism wave increased.

Recommendations

The country should put on its whole efforts in increasing the inflow of investment by controlling the terrorism in the country. Pakistan should not involve in others' issues and focus on bettering its own internal matters. The economy is the most important factor to run the country and improving the standard of living of the people should be made the first target. The country should try to improve its spoiled business image in front of the world market by providing local businesses to come forward and built a better repute. The country should also be built stronger relations with the foreign investors by providing them more opportunities and incentives and security of the investment so that more investors can be attracted towards Pakistan and the business environment can be flourished.

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